

Notes

Stability of Ternary Solubilized Solutions (Spectrophotometric Measurements)

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VON BUZAGH and McBain etc.¹⁻⁵ held controversial opinions for the thermodynamic stability of solubilized solutions. Recently the author studied a few properties⁶⁻¹⁰ and proved that these solutions were thermodynamically unstable as suggested by Chatterjee¹¹. In this paper, measurements of percentage transmission in a ternary solubilized solution (H_2O +sodium oleate+oleic acid) are reported and the results are compared with those from conductivity, viscosity, surface tension, calorimetric measurements.

Experimental

Material used: Oleic acid (A.R.), Sodium oleate (A.R.). They were purified further with standard methods. Specially prepared conductivity water (sp. conductivity $2.78 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) at 35° was used at pH, 4.5.

Preparation of solutions (as given earlier)¹².

Apparatus

The spectrophotometer (Unicam Sp. 500) was calibrated with (M/100) potassium dichromate solution in the range $\lambda = 250 \text{ \AA}$ to $\lambda = 800 \text{ \AA}$ at 35° . The slit correction was frequently applied and the overlapping in the visible and ultraviolet region was also removed from time to time.

Procedure: The solvent and the samples of the two binary systems were kept in the two quartz cells. Using the null deflection method the optical density was measured in the range $\lambda = 500 \text{ \AA}$ to $\lambda = 800 \text{ \AA}$ against concentrations in order to detect a common maxima but instead of a common maxima, a common minima $\lambda = 530$ was obtained to study the ternary solubilized solution.

Experimental Results and Discussion

(a) From the Fig. 1, it is seen that in the two binary systems, homogeneous curves *a*, *b* were obtained but in the ternary system in which concentration of oleic acid was fixed ($1.518 \times 10^{-7} M$) and increasing amount of sodium oleate was added keeping the total volume constant, a typical curve "a" in Fig. 1 was observed, when transmission percentage was plotted against log concentration. From the curve 'a', it is seen that transmission

increased along the line *xy* with the increase of concentration. The solution became transparent at *y*. On increasing the concentration further, transmission decreased and the curve attained the minimum

Fig. 1. Fixed conc. of oleic acid used, (a) $1.518 \times 10^{-7} M$, (b) $1.518 \times 10^{-6} M$, (c) $1.518 \times 10^{-5} M$.

value at *Z*. Now the solution was turbid and cluster assembled. When the concentration was increased further, transmission (1/O.D.) increased along *ZL* and the solution became transparent. When the concentration was increased further, transmission followed the line *IN*, turning the solution more and more turbid.

(b) Now the experiment was repeated with oleic acid of concentration $1.518 \times 10^{-6} M$. When transmission was plotted against concentration (curve *b*), a kink was formed at *Y'*, in the line *X'Y'* due to cluster assemblance by van der Waals' forces. As the concentration was increased further, this curve like the curve 'a' moved up to *Z'*, crossed the curve 'a', reached *L'*, and formed a peak indicating that this solution, was more transparent than the solution (a).

(c) Now the experiment was repeated with another sample of oleic acid of conc. $1.518 \times 10^{-5} M$ and sodium oleate concentrations was increased gradually. When transmission values were plotted against concentration, (curve *c*), a straight line was observed (portion *x''y''*) in the concentration range $1 \times 10^{-7} M$ to $1 \times 10^{-6} M$. At *Y''* the curve turned, indicating the turbidity of the solution and forming a kink. Then the curve moved upward and a peak at *Z''* was noticed where the solution became transparent. Thus two kinks were again obtained. Since the changes at the first kink were very small, both the binary solutions were mixed in equimolar ratio having equal volume (1 : 1), but in increasing concentrations in order to get better results. It was observed from Fig. 2 that again two kinks were obtained.

Thus it is quite clear that the structure of solubilized solutions was quite different from the binary solutions.

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In order to study the nature of the solubilized solutions, surface tension, viscosity, conductivity, zeta potential, of the binary and ternary solutions were measured⁶⁻¹⁰. In case of the binary mixtures,

Fig. 2. Systems (a) Sodium oleate + H₂O, (b) Oleic acid + H₂O, (c) Sodium oleate + H₂O + Oleic acid.

homogeneous curves were obtained while in the ternary solubilized solutions, two peaks were again obtained. The following table gives the concentrations at which the two peaks were formed by studying different properties.

TABLE I.

Properties studies	Concentrations of forming the peaks		References
	First	Second	
Conductivity	$1.338 \times 10^{-6} M$	$3.043 \times 10^{-4} M$	6
Surface tension	6.34	0.95	8
Zeta potential	7.9	1.32	12
Transmission	3.16	3.82	
Viscosity	0.27	2.53	7

It is observed from the table that the two peaks or kinks were not formed at the same concentrations suggesting that during solubilization unstable loose combination of molecules were formed for a very short time making the solution heterogeneous and unstable. Had the solution been homogeneous and stable, kinks or peaks would not have formed¹³.

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References

- VON BUZAGH, *Kolloid Z.*, 1932, **47**, 370.
- MCBAIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 52.
- GURUZTSCH, *Kolloid Z.*, 1933, **160**, 300.
- LAING, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, **40**, 1099.
- P. A. WINSOR, *Chem. Rev.*, 1968, **40**, 1.
- B. SWAROOP, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1971, **41A**, 74.
- B. SWAROOP, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1971, **41A**, 33.
- B. SWAROOP, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, 1971, **41A**, 121.
- B. SWAROOP, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1972, **251**, 27.
- B. SWAROOP, *Kolloid Z.*, 1972, **250**, 964.
- A. C. CHATTERJI, private communication, 1965.
- B. SWAROOP, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 799.
- B. SWAROOP, *Colloid & Polymer*, 1974, **252**, 240.
- B. SWAROOP, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **250**, 2.
- G. SINGH, Private Communication, 1975.

Chlorination of 2-Amino Thiazoles and the Use of Chlorinated Thiazoles as Possible Fungicides

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IN view of the good response of 2-amino 4-aryl substituted thiazoles and their derivatives as good fungicides¹, it was considered of interest to examine the fungicidal property of a few 2-amino 4-aryl substituted thiazoles and their 5-chloro derivatives, so that a comparison of their fungicidal activity would be possible. The presence of liophilic and polar substituents like aryl and amino groups in the thiazole nucleus, as found here, is expected to augment the fungitoxic property still further². Introduction of halogens³, particularly chlorine, into the thiazole nucleus is expected to increase the fungicidal activity considerably.

2-Amino-4-aryl thiazoles have been synthesized by condensing nine different ketones with thiourea in presence of bromine which is used as the condensing agent⁴. These 2-amino thiazoles were then chlorinated with dry chlorine gas in glacial acetic acid medium, after protecting the amino groups by converting them to their respective hydrochloride salts. In each case a mono chloro derivative resulted.

It has been assumed that the chlorine atom is attached to the thiazole nucleus at C₅-position as the activity of C₅ in the thiazole nucleus is maximum, particularly when there is a substituent at C₂-position⁵. This assumption is further based on the evidences of Garreau⁶ and Ganapathi and Venkataraman⁷ and Mahapatra¹¹. As in this series of thiazoles, the C₄-position is occupied by an aryl group and C₅-position is free; the chlorine atom should enter C₅-position, which generally acts as the *para* carbon atom to the NH₂ group, the orienting group in the molecule. This assumption is further supported by the fact that the chlorinated thiazoles do not undergo coupling with diazotised aniline, which generally takes place at C₅-position, if it is free⁸. The possibility of chlorine atom going to the aromatic part carrying a hydroxy group at C₄-position is also discarded on the ground that the chlorinated compounds do not undergo coupling with diazotised aniline as they should, if chlorine would have entered the phenyl nucleus at C₄-position. This indirectly shows that C₅-position of the thiazole nucleus is not free. This assumption gains further support from the fact that due to the polar effect of the substituents at C₂- and C₄-positions of a heterocyclic compound like thiazole, the newly entering chlorine atom generally attaches to C₅-position⁹.

Experimental

2-Amino-4-phenyl-thiazole: The method used for the preparation of the thiazole was that of Dash and Mahapatra⁴.